

The Basis Set Truncation Error Revisited: Comparison of Multiwavelet and Gaussian Basis Sets for Computing

Properties from First Principles

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Abstract

A set of 225 molecules and 5726 reactions are used to examine errors present in linear-combination of atomic orbital (LCAO) calculations using standard atom-centered Gaussian basis sets at the Hartree-Fock and density functional theory levels of theory. We advance beyond previous studies by extending the test set to include heavier atoms, by probing the origin and nature of errors in LCAO calculations including transferability of basis sets between HF and different DFT functionals, by reporting computational times for the multiwavelet calculations and by examining errors in reaction energies, where errors are computed by comparing LCAO results to numerically converged solutions in the MW basis. Calculations in uncontracted basis sets quantify the different errors arising from contraction and incompleteness in the primitive Gaussian basis. Analysis indicates significantly larger errors associated with atoms in the third or lower rows of the periodic table.

1 Introduction

Motivated by recent studies and discussion [1–3], we revisit the errors present in linear-combination of atomic orbital (LCAO) calculations using standard atom-centered Gaussian basis sets at the Hartree-Fock (HF) and density functional theory (DFT) levels of theory. Converged HF calculations are an essential foundation for subsequent accurate many-body studies, and a detailed understanding of basis set error is essential to obtain the full predictive power from DFT calculations in finite basis sets using approximate exchange correlation functionals. The authors extensively use both Gaussian and [4] and multiwavelet (MW) [5] basis sets, and our perspective is that there is no perfect basis — it is simply a matter of picking the right tool for the right job. The main purpose of the paper is to provide and examine data to inform such decisions, which includes computational cost as well as accuracy and the nature of errors. We advance beyond previous studies by extending the test set to include heavier atoms, by probing the origin and nature of errors in LCAO calculations including transferability between HF and different DFT functionals, by examining errors in reaction energies and by reporting computational times for the multiwavelet calculations. Since we anticipate this heavily curated data set to be a valuable community resource, in the supplementary data we provide spread sheets summarizing the results as well as the full set of scripts and raw output files.

In prior work, we [6–9] and others [10–12], have established multiresolution analysis (MRA) with multiwavelets as a practical tool for computing ground and excited state properties with guaranteed accuracy, regardless of the physics. Convergence of MW results to sub-micro-Hartree accuracy for both HF and DFT has already been established for atoms and small molecules [6, 10, 13], and demonstrated for small atoms and molecules in atto-second and intensely ionizing IR laser pulses [14]. The guarantee of accuracy [15] arises from dynamic adaptive refinement of the underlying multiwavelet basis to meet the requested accuracy of computation. Realizing this in practice requires careful analysis and implementation, with subsequent verification, which includes comparison with both analytic results as well as converged data from other computational methods, including Gaussian LCAO expansions.

The dynamic mesh refinement/coarsening introduces numerical errors (basis incompleteness or truncation error) that are not correlated between independent calculations, and hence do not cancel in taking chemical energy differences. Thus, total MW energies must be computed to the desired accuracy of any energy differences (or response theory used to obtain differences directly), which becomes a burden for very large systems or systems with heavy atoms unless effective-core or pseudo-potentials are employed (all computations in this paper are all electron). A final source of error is regularizing the singularity of the point nuclear charge through the use of a smooth potential [5] for which an estimate from perturbation theory provides precise control over the error introduced. Note that this error is systematic and largely cancels in taking energy differences. These errors are examined in more detail in Section 2.

Increased accuracy comes with additional computational cost, which is another limit on the accuracy attainable in practice. However, key computational steps, such as the computation of the Coulomb potential or orbital update scale exactly linearly in the number of significant coefficients, and other steps such as computation of the kinetic and potential energy matrices or application of the Hartree-Fock exchange operator [6] have an effective sub-quadratic scaling with system size in localized orbitals. These properties hold at any finite accuracy of computation, which is in sharp contrast to Gaussian LCAO approaches. The introduction of polarization and especially diffuse functions into a Gaussian basis set greatly increases the cost of computation, with the matrix representation of many operators (e.g., the Fock operator or the density matrix) becoming effectively dense and the condition number of the overlap matrix becoming large. These two problems conspire to make it very hard to translate to large molecules the success of Gaussian methods in performing demonstrably-converged calculations on small and medium-sized molecules.

Part of the computational advantage of MW methods for HF and DFT is that they only compute with the occupied orbitals. It is possible to solve for a few virtual orbitals assuming that they are bound, which is usually not the case for HF. Other operators can define more strongly localized virtual orbitals such as used in previous numerical studies [16], but it is clear MW do not provide an ideal framework for defining a large set of virtual orbitals for subsequent many-body computations, and that Gaussians retain a strong advantage in this respect. Recent work by Valeev [17] has

demonstrated use of the same C++ software to solve for PNOs using either Gaussian or MRA approaches.

Computation of forces in the MW basis [13] is efficient due to the effectively complete basis, however, numerical noise in the density near the nucleus makes it hard to attain high accuracy. Indeed, this (along with speed) is the main reason the default MADNESS smoothing parameter is set to $10^{-4}E_h$ rather than smaller, since the smoother potential amplifies noise less.

In the following, we adopt much the same approach as [1] by identifying a test suite of molecules and computing energies and other properties using the effectively exact MW approach and using a wide range of contracted Gaussian basis sets for HF and several commonly-used density functionals. We examine results in uncontracted primitive sets to explore the origin of errors and the transferability of basis sets from one functional to another. We conclude by examining errors in a large set of reactions constructed from the test set, and discussing the timing of the MW calculations.

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2 Methods

Density functional theory and Hartree-Fock calculations were carried out in both the multi-wavelet basis of MADNESS (#06572b98) and a progression of spherical bases in NWChem (version 6.6). The functionals used were SVWN5(LDA) [18], B3LYP [19], and PBE0 [20]. The basis sets used in NWChem were 3-21G [21], 6-31G* [22], cc-pvXz [23], cc-pcvXz [24], aug-cc-pvXz [23], and aug-cc-pcvXz [24] where X = D,T,Q as well as the pc-segY [25] series for Y = 1,2,3 and aug-pc-segZ [25] for Z=1,2. To explore the effect of contraction, both contracted and uncontracted basis sets were used. All geometries were taken from the SI of [1] or from the NIST database [26] (see Supporting Information for complete listing). All calculations for which a time is reported were run on a single compute node of the Seawulf cluster, consisting of 2 Intel Xeon CPU E5-2683 v3 @ 2.00 GHz with 28 cores total and 128GB of memory.

NWChem calculations were performed using 26 MPI processes, and NWChem separately uses a communication thread for Global Arrays. Open shell calculations were spin and symmetry unrestricted, and all integrals were computed on the fly using the `direct` keyword; otherwise default parameters were used except as needed to obtain convergence to the lowest energy state. Input files and job scripts for both MADNESS and NWChem can be found in the supporting information.

MADNESS calculations were run using 2 MPI processes, each bound to a different socket, and 11 threads per process. Four molecules (bromoform, carbon tetrabromide, nitrogen tribromide, and phosphorous tribromide) required more memory for MADNESS. They were run on two nodes with the same number of MPI process and threads, with one MPI process per node. Default parameters were used for everything other than smoothing parameter for the nuclear potential that was set to introduce a maximum error in the energy of $10^{-6} E_h/\text{atom}$.

There are three sources of error in our MW results (1) smoothing of the nuclear charge, (2) convergence error in the wave function with the error in the energy being quadratic in this error, as is also the case for LCAO, and (3) truncation error in the numerical basis that is controlled by a single input parameter (ϵ in the paper body). In Table 1 we provide representative results demonstrating (1) numerical convergence for atoms and small molecules relevant to this study, (2)

that the parameters used in this study (the *default* parameters for MADNESS with smoothing errors reduced to $10^{-6} E_h$) deliver better than $10^{-4} E_h/\text{atom}$ error in total energies, and (3) that chemical energy differences are obtained to 0.02 kcal/mol or better.

There were a few instances when open-shell molecules converged to different states with MADNESS and NWChem. After ensuring that the NWChem solution was the lowest energy state, MADNESS was given the converged NWChem wave-function in the aug-cc-pvqz basis as a starting guess. These data were used in the accuracy comparisons only.

Substantial effort was invested in validating the calculations. An initial check was that the MW energy be lowest, and subsequently the energies of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) were compared, with roughly 3 significant figure agreement anticipated for the aug-cc-pvqz basis. Subsequently, outliers in errors or trends were examined. The most problems were observed with open shell systems with symmetry in diffuse basis sets, for which we commonly disabled symmetry and sought the lowest energy occupation pattern by first converging a closed-shell ion and adding electrons back one at a time.

Total energies (E_h)				
System	Default	Current	High	Reference
H	-0.499 953 5	-0.499 999 5	-0.500 000 0	-0.5
Be	-14.572 937 5	-14.573 022 1	-14.573 023 2	-14.573 023 2
C	-37.693 648 0	-37.693 739 0	-37.693 740 5	
N	-54.404 453 8	-54.404 546 5	-54.404 548 4	
F	-99.416 208 4	-99.416 304 1	-99.416 306 2	
P	-340.719 167 8	-340.719 269 4	-340.719 275 5	
Mg	-199.614 133 2	-199.614 632 3	-199.614 636 7	-199.614 636 3
Br	-2572.448 390 1	-2572.448 501 1	-2572.448 525 5	
Sr	-3131.545 547 4	-3131.545 656 6	-3131.545 685 5	-3131.545 686
NH ₃	-56.225 221 4	-56.225 520 8	-56.225 525 8	
PH ₃	-342.494 924 4	-342.495 214 6	-342.495 219 5	
HBr	-2573.052 107 0	-2573.052 269 0	-2573.052 311 0	
BeF ₂	-213.789 779 9	-213.790 054 0	-213.790 061 0	
MgF ₂	-398.730 393 2	-398.730 682 5	-398.730 703 7	
SrF ₂	-3330.684 584 7	-3330.684 885 4	-3330.684 944 9	
Atomization energies (kcal./mol.)				
System	Default	Current	High	Curr. -High
NH ₃	201.372	201.415	201.417	0.002
PH ₃	173.127	173.159	173.158	0.001
HBr	65.113	65.116	65.126	0.010
BeF ₂	241.231	241.230	241.231	0.001
MgF ₂	178.114	177.863	177.871	0.008
SrF ₂	192.407	192.408	192.424	0.020
Dipole moments (a.u.)				
System	Default	Current	High	Curr. -High
NH ₃	0.608 674	0.608 617	0.608 079	0.000 54
PH ₃	0.300 499	0.300 191	0.300 134	0.000 06
HBr	0.371 128	0.371 028	0.370 903	0.000 13
Geometries (a.u.)				
System	Geometry			
NH ₃	N(-0.201,0,0); H(0.468,1.763,0); H(0.468,-0.882,±1.527)			
HBr	Br(0,0,-0.074); H(0,0,2.595)			
BeF ₂	Be(0,0,0), F(0,0,±2.627)			
MgF ₂	Mg(0,0,0), F(0,0,±3.286)			
SrF ₂	Sr(0,0,0), F(0,0,±4.112)			

Table 1: Hartree-Fock results obtained using (1) **default** MADNESS parameters (truncation threshold $\epsilon=10^{-6}$; density convergence threshold $\Delta\rho=10^{-4}$; smoothing error $\tau=10^{-4}E_h/\text{atom}$), (2) **current** parameters used in this study which are default parameters modified with $\tau=10^{-6}$, and (3) **high** accuracy settings $\epsilon=10^{-8}$; $\Delta\rho=10^{-6}$; $\tau=10^{-7}$). Reference data from [27]. Open shell systems employ spin-unrestricted HF.

Results and discussion

In the following, we focus (for brevity and due to their systematic design) upon results for the correlation consistent and pc-seg basis set families — the SI contains data on additional basis sets.

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Total Energy

While total energies are not of direct interest, we will see below that errors in chemically-relevant energies are correlated with errors in total energies. The difference in total energy as calculated with MW versus the LCAO-MO approach with members of the Gaussian correlation-consistent basis set is shown in Figures 1 – 4. Overall systematic convergence to the MW result is apparent as the Gaussian basis is improved. The larger errors in each series of plots are from sulfur hexafluoride and the molecules containing bromide, and the smallest error for a given number of electrons is typically a hydrocarbon alkane chain.

While augmenting the basis with diffuse functions is important for accurate chemical energy differences, augmentation has little effect on the total energies. The correlation-consistent basis sets were designed (i.e., selection of exponents and contraction coefficients) for HF plus *ab initio* correlation, and as previous authors have noted [25], the accuracy obtained for HF is not fully transferable to DFT.

To disentangle the contraction error from incompleteness in the primitive Gaussian set, we performed calculations with uncontracted correlation-consistent Gaussian basis sets with HF results in 5 and DFT-PBE0 results reported in Figure 6. It is immediately apparent there is negligible contraction error for HF whereas for DFT-PBE0 and other functionals there is very substantial reduction in error by uncontracting especially for heavier elements — the five largest changes when uncontracting in any of the basis sets were from CBr₄, PBr₃, NBr₃, CHBr₃, and SiCl₄. Data in the SI demonstrates that contraction error was significantly larger for DFT-LDA, compared to DFT-PBE0. Upon uncontraction the total energy errors were similar in magnitude for both HF and the DFT functionals.

The pc-seg family [25] of basis sets was designed for DFT calculations and was contracted to be more transferrable between functionals. In Figures 7 and 8 we report the errors in the total energies for HF and DFT-PBE0, respectively, using the aug-pcseg-2 basis, both contracted and uncontracted. The contracted aug-pcseg-2 basis provides errors of similar magnitude to that of the comparable aug-cc-pVTZ basis for both HF and DFT. However, uncontraction significantly reduces

Figure 1: For HF, errors in total energy in Gaussian basis sets. Error values displayed in this and all subsequent figures (unless noted otherwise) are the Gaussian basis set energy minus MW energy.

Figure 2: For DFT-LDA, errors in total energy in Gaussian basis sets.

Figure 3: For DFT-B3LYP, errors in total energy in Gaussian basis sets.

Figure 4: For DFT-PBE0, errors in total energy in Gaussian basis sets.

the errors, indicating significant contraction error. Moreover, the errors in the uncontracted pc-seg DFT energies are smaller than those in the uncontracted aug-cc-pVTZ basis, indicating that the pc-seg primitive basis is indeed better adapted to one-body models.

In the following sections we focus upon errors in atomization and reaction energies that are a major objective for computational quantum chemistry [28,29].

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Figure 5: For HF, errors in total energy in contracted and uncontracted (labelled “unc-*) correlation consistent Gaussian basis sets. The final column is the contracted basis set energy minus the uncontracted basis set energy.

Figure 6: For DFT-PBE0, errors in total energy in contracted and uncontracted correlation-consistent Gaussian basis sets. The final column of Figures is the contracted basis set energy minus the uncontracted basis set energy.

Figure 7: For HF, errors in total energy in contracted and uncontracted pc-seg Gaussian basis sets. The final column is the contracted basis set energy minus the uncontracted basis set energy.

Figure 8: For DFT-PBE0, errors in total energy in contracted and uncontracted pc-seg Gaussian basis sets. The final column is the contracted basis set energy minus the uncontracted basis set energy.

Atomization energies

The atomization energies (HF and DFT-PBE0 data in Figures 9 and 10, respectively) illustrate some, but not all, of the trends that will be observed in reaction energies. As with the reaction energies, discussed below, the Gaussian basis sets have the most difficulty describing third row elements and perhaps also fluorine. The eight largest outliers for the DFT atomization energies are sulfur hexafluoride, sulfur dioxide, phosphorus pentafluoride, phosphorus dioxide, tetrafluorosilane, chlorine trifluoride, phosphorus trifluoride, and dimethyl sulfoxide. Figures 11 and 12 display significant correlation in the magnitude of errors in the total energy and atomization energies — i.e., imperfect systematic cancellation of error. Addition of diffuse functions and uncontracting the basis set do not significantly change overall errors in the atomization energies. Some of the errors are negative (i.e., the Gaussian basis set atomization energy is too large), which we attribute to basis set superposition error. We note that Peterson and collaborators have developed basis sets with additional freedom for semi-core electrons [30] and effective core-polarization potentials [31] in order to address this issue. In the section on reactions below (2) we provide results with polarized core basis sets.

Figure 9: For HF, errors in atomization energies in Gaussian basis sets for all 225 molecules in the set. Values displayed are MW atomization energy minus the Gaussian basis set value.

Figure 10: For DFT-PBE0, errors in atomization energies in Gaussian basis sets.

Figure 11: For HF, errors in atomization energies versus errors in total energies.

Figure 12: For DFT-PBE0, errors in atomization energies versus errors in total energies.

Reactions

From the 225 molecules in the test set we identified 5726 unique reactions with the form $aA + bB \rightarrow cC$, defined as

$$E_{\text{rxn}} = cE(C) - [aE(A) + bE(B)]. \quad (1)$$

subject to the constraint $a, b, c \leq 36$. We allowed for $A = B$ or $A = C$, so that reactions of the form $A \rightarrow B$ and $aA + bB \rightarrow cA$ are included. The vast majority of the reactions (5163) involved only hydrocarbons or di-hydrogen. All 5726 reactions can be found in the SI under file name `abtoc_rxns.txt`. Here, we focus on the results for HF and DFT-PBE0. The results for DFT-B3LYP and DFT-LDA show the same trends and are covered in the SI.

Looking first at just reactions involving hydrocarbons (Table 2), high accuracy (with the mean and median errors and standard deviation all less than 0.1 kcal/mol/atom, and the maximum outlier significantly less than 1 kcal/mol) is readily obtained and the errors show systematic convergence and size dependence.

Such accuracy and consistency are not as easily attained for all molecules (Table 3). In Figures 13 and 14 we show the full set of reaction energy differences, divided into those that include third-row or heavier elements and those that involve only first and second-row elements. The value plotted is the MW reaction energy minus the Gaussian basis set reaction energy, with the reaction direction as given in Eq. (1).

Theory	Basis	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	Max Dev.
HF	cc-pvdz	2.198	1.976	1.495	4.919
	cc-pvtz	0.457	0.513	0.223	0.742
	cc-pvqz	0.059	0.056	0.035	0.115
	aug-cc-pvdz	1.920	1.698	1.210	4.260
	aug-cc-pvtz	0.230	0.226	0.110	0.425
	aug-cc-pvqz	0.072	0.066	0.051	0.210
	unc-aug-cc-pvdz	1.110	0.755	1.034	4.098
	unc-aug-cc-pvtz	0.119	0.120	0.080	0.258
	unc-aug-cc-pvqz	0.054	0.044	0.047	0.179

Table 2: Statistical analysis of the absolute value of errors in correlation consistent Gaussian basis set Hartree-Fock reaction energies involving only hydrocarbons (kcal/mol). Errors with DFT functionals are of similar magnitude.

Theory	Basis	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	Max Dev.
HF	cc-pvdz	7.312	4.486	8.323	155.766
	cc-pvtz	1.215	0.749	1.676	40.661
	cc-pvqz	0.396	0.235	0.617	15.243
	aug-cc-pvdz	7.197	4.381	8.381	117.131
	aug-cc-pvtz	0.590	0.326	0.989	29.714
	aug-cc-pvqz	0.158	0.085	0.374	13.142
	unc-aug-cc-pvdz	5.186	3.211	6.264	121.900
	unc-aug-cc-pvtz	0.531	0.300	0.916	29.067
	unc-aug-cc-pvqz	0.158	0.085	0.372	13.019
	cc-pcvdz	6.875	4.270	7.853	149.916
	cc-pcvtz	1.192	0.737	1.542	25.372
	cc-pcvqz	0.445	0.277	0.565	9.495
	aug-cc-pcvdz	6.692	4.018	7.830	110.845
	aug-cc-pcvtz	0.520	0.315	0.640	10.650
	aug-cc-pcvqz	0.147	0.093	0.165	1.797
	pcseg-1	4.209	2.433	5.239	84.867
	pcseg-2	1.149	0.610	1.726	45.010
	pcseg-3	0.592	0.251	1.228	43.651
	aug-pcseg-1	7.581	4.930	8.284	61.158
	aug-pcseg-2	1.109	0.656	1.574	45.272
unc-aug-pcseg-2	0.366	0.194	1.096	44.501	
DFT-PBE0	cc-pvdz	9.254	5.814	10.205	136.586
	cc-pvtz	0.984	0.522	1.854	35.315
	cc-pvqz	0.599	0.335	0.883	14.010
	aug-cc-pvdz	7.697	4.216	9.073	106.628
	aug-cc-pvtz	0.823	0.434	1.236	28.057
	aug-cc-pvqz	0.330	0.194	0.499	15.955
	unc-aug-cc-pvdz	4.754	3.001	5.761	103.233
	unc-aug-cc-pvtz	0.607	0.327	1.070	28.129
	unc-aug-cc-pvqz	0.290	0.139	0.507	16.147
	cc-pevdz	8.988	5.701	9.860	128.737
	cc-pcvtz	1.396	0.838	1.984	35.178
	cc-pcvqz	0.544	0.314	0.819	14.193
	aug-cc-pcvdz	7.248	3.955	8.534	99.492
	aug-cc-pcvtz	0.527	0.309	0.776	16.387
	aug-cc-pcvqz	0.247	0.141	0.292	2.398
	pcseg-1	5.039	3.189	5.653	73.457
	pcseg-2	0.794	0.407	1.131	17.539
	pcseg-3	0.340	0.181	0.515	15.708
	aug-pcseg-1	7.126	4.449	7.893	53.705
	aug-pcseg-2	0.475	0.286	0.664	17.698
unc-aug-pcseg-2	0.345	0.210	0.575	17.493	

Table 3: Statistical analysis of the absolute value of errors in reaction energies for all reactions (kcal/mol).

The statistics show that in these families of Gaussian basis sets it is possible to attain chemical accuracy (i.e., better than 1 kcal/mol) *on average*, with this accuracy attained by the augmented triple-zeta quality basis sets. However, there remain very significant outliers with errors that are at least 10 times greater. Errors (both mean and outliers) in the smaller basis sets of the quality commonly used for large molecule calculations (e.g., polarized double-zeta) are even larger and can exceed the scale of errors introduced by choice of density functional. The basis set errors do appear to be roughly transferable between DFT functionals — i.e., for a given basis set both average and outlier errors are similar in magnitude for all functionals. By separating the reaction set into those involving only first- or second-row elements and those with heavier elements (figures 13 and 14) and focusing upon the aug-cc-pVTZ and aug-cc-pVQZ basis sets which are converged for the lighter elements, we see that the larger errors and outliers are all associated with the heavier elements. As noted above, the need for core and semi-core polarization and correlation functions for heavier elements is already understood [30,31].

Basis	Reaction Number	Reactants		Products		Error (kcal/mol)
cc-pvdz	5189	4 O ₃	3 P ₄	12 PO	136.6	
	1789	3 cyclobutene	4 O ₃	6 CH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	86.2	
	1218	3 bicyclo[1.1.0]butane	4 O ₃	6 CH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	84.5	
	4844	3 methylenecyclopropane	4 O ₃	6 CH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	82.0	
cc-pvtz	5189	4 O ₃	3 P ₄	12 PO	35.3	
	2823	3 2-butyne	4 O ₃	6 CH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	34.3	
	1789	3 cyclobutene	4 O ₃	6 CH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	34.0	
	4844	3 methylenecyclopropane	4 O ₃	6 CH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	33.8	
cc-pvqz	3569	5 glyoxal trans	2 CH ₃ OH	6 CH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	14.0	
	5189	4 O ₃	3 P ₄	12 PO	13.4	
	2823	3 2-butyne	4 O ₃	6 CH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	13.1	
	1218	3 bicyclo[1.1.0]butane	4 O ₃	6 CH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	13.1	
aug-cc-pvdz	5189	4 O ₃	3 P ₄	12 PO	106.6	
	4610	24 CH	1 nonane	11 propyne	66.8	
	5694	5 S ₂	2 SF ₆	12 SF	65.9	
	5188	2 O ₃	3 P ₂	6 PO	63.2	
aug-cc-pvtz	5694	5 S ₂	2 SF ₆	12 SF	28.1	
	5189	4 O ₃	3 P ₄	12 PO	26.7	
	5188	2 O ₃	3 P ₂	6 PO	15.8	
	5692	2 SO ₂	1 S ₂	4 SO	14.0	
aug-cc-pvqz	5694	5 S ₂	2 SF ₆	12 SF	16.0	
	5189	4 O ₃	3 P ₄	12 PO	11.8	
	5188	2 O ₃	3 P ₂	6 PO	7.7	
	5692	2 SO ₂	1 S ₂	4 SO	7.6	
aug-cc-pcvqz	4610	24 CH	1 nonane	11 propyne	2.4	
	4605	26 CH	2 nonane	11 2-butyne	2.4	
	4614	28 CH	3 nonane	11 spiropentane	2.4	
	4604	24 CH	1 nonane	11 cyclopropene	2.3	

Table 4: Largest four outliers in the DFT-PBE0 reaction energies for several basis sets; other functionals behave similarly. The absolute value of the error is reported, and the reaction number matches the data provided in the SI.

The largest outlier errors (Table 4) in un-augmented basis sets are associated with atoms with anionic character. In augmented basis sets the outliers are dominated by heavier elements (notably S and P in this test set). For instance, at the HF level of theory in the cc-pvNz (N=d,t,q) basis sets with/without augmentation and also in the aug-cc-pcvqz basis that includes core polarization the largest outlier was $4\text{O}_3 + 3\text{P}_4 \rightarrow 12\text{PO}$. Most (but not all) outliers are also associated with a large number of fragments with many bonds being formed/broken. This is good news in that the error per fragment or bond broken can be small even in these outliers, but also bad news in that errors can systematically accumulate.

All of the outlier reactions regardless of the participating elements involve a significant change in at least one of the coordination, bonding patterns, strain, or charge distribution. For example, at the DFT-PBE0 level of theory (Table 4), the aug-cc-pcvtz basis completely removes heavier elements from the top four outliers which are instead all reactions involving hydrocarbons with a very large number of fragments and significant change in bonding patterns. These reactions thus expose basis deficiencies such as inadequate polarization or lack of diffuse functions that lead to unbalanced or even reinforcing errors between reactants and products. These are familiar concerns to any computational chemist and homodesmotic reactions [32, 33] or computation of trends are widely-used approaches to engineer increased cancellation of such errors.

A comparison of reactions involving one or more open-shell molecules to reactions with only closed shell molecules suggests that open-shell character alone is not a dominant effect in the errors (more details can be found in the SI). The open-shell molecules were by far the hardest to ensure completely comparable results between the MW and atom-centered basis sets. We attribute most of these difficulties to use of spin and symmetry unrestricted calculations (which are typically used in DFT studies of open shell system and is all that MADNESS presently supports) and the additional freedom in the MW basis permitting greater spin-polarization of the nominally closed-shell states. We anticipate even smaller errors (Gaussian versus MW) would be obtained for open-shell systems by using spin-restricted methods.

Figure 13: For HF, errors in reaction energies in correlation consistent Gaussian basis sets separated into reactions involving **(Top)** no third-row and lower elements and **(Bottom)** third-row and lower elements.

Figure 14: For DFT-PBE0, errors in reaction energies in correlation Gaussian basis sets separated into reactions involving (**Top**) no third-row and lower elements and (**Bottom**) third-row and lower elements.

Dipoles

The errors in dipoles computed with DFT-PBE0 and Gaussian basis sets are shown in Figure 15. Errors for HF and other DFT functionals are similar. Looking at the aug-cc-pVQZ basis set, the three largest outliers are NaCl (-0.07114 Debye), NaF (-0.07174 Debye) and NaOH (-0.09554 Debye). For DFT-PBE0 (and also for DFT-B3LYP in the SI data) the molecule boron monocarbide is a clear outlier in the larger basis sets with a dipole difference value of -0.09 Debye. This difference is due to the MW basis converging to a different but nearly energetically degenerate state, even when starting the MW basis calculation with a converged Gaussian basis set solution. The discussion about open-shell systems at the end of the immediately preceding section is relevant to this point.

Timing

Detailed analysis of the performance of MADNESS is pending completion of optimizations to the orbital localization and Hartree-Fock exchange. However, even the preliminary data illustrate several key points. The total computer time for all HF calculations is presented in Figure 16 against the number of electrons in the system for the MW calculations and the number of basis functions for Gaussian basis set calculations. For the largest 25 % of the calculations, as judged by the number of basis functions and number of electrons for the Gaussian and MW calculations, respectively, the results have been fitted to a simple power law (i.e., $T(N) = aN^b$) in order to estimate the *effective* scaling of computational cost with system size, with b reported in the figure as dy/dx , i.e., the slope of the log-log plot). The molecules are insufficiently large to extract the true asymptotic scaling, which in practice is not relevant since different algorithms and representations become relevant at larger scales. In a Gaussian calculation the cost is driven by the number of integrals which is dependent upon the number of basis functions that depends irregularly upon the number of electrons, whereas in MADNESS the computational cost is controlled by the number of significant MW coefficients that is strongly linearly dependent upon the number of electrons (in a localized basis).

A few clear trends emerge. As expected, adding more polarization functions to the basis set, as

is done in the cc-pVNZ family, and adding diffuse functions, as done in the aug-cc-pVNZ family, adds significantly to the computational cost. For high accuracy calculations on even moderately large systems, the near-quadratic scaling of the MW approach makes this a cost-effective alternative to the traditional LCAO-MO approach.

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Figure 15: For DFT-PBE0, errors in dipole moments in Gaussian basis sets. Values displayed are MW minus Gaussian basis sets.

Figure 16: For HF, total wall time per electron for MW and per basis function for Gaussian basis sets.

3 Conclusions

From our systematic comparison of converged MW and Gaussian basis set results in several density functionals we draw several main conclusions, most of which are already represented in the literature but are not routinely reflected in widely-used computational protocols.

- Errors in atomic and molecular total energies are significantly correlated with errors in chemical energy differences due to imperfect cancellation of systematic errors, inadequate polarization of atoms in molecules, and basis set superposition error.
- For first and second period atoms (H-Ne), widely-used families of basis sets are capable of systematically approaching the converged numerical results for chemical reactions. For hydrocarbons the cc-pvtz basis reduces the mean, median, standard deviation, and maximum deviation well below 1 kcal/mole. For other atoms augmentation with diffuse functions is necessary.
- For heavier atoms in widely-used basis set families, there remain outlier reactions with errors of 10 kcal/mol or much more that are not remedied by uncontracting. This incompleteness in the primitive set is in part associated with inadequate polarization of the inner valence or outer core states as already identified by Peterson and collaborators [30,31]. To reduce the errors of outliers close to 1 kcal/mol it is necessary to employ augmented, polarized, quadruple-zeta basis sets with core polarization (Table 3). However, such large basis sets are very rarely employed in DFT calculations, and commonly-used DZP-quality basis sets have outliers with errors over 100 kcal/mol.
- A corollary to the preceding point is that estimating basis set error for molecules with heavy atoms by extrapolating results in standard basis set families without core polarization (e.g., the aug-pvNz with N=d,t,q,...) can suggest convergence to the basis set limit but in actuality produce incorrect values.
- The importance of model chemistries defined by both DFT functional+basis (and any other parameters controlling error or reproducibility) is emphasized by the complexity and expense

of reliably reducing errors in Gaussian basis set reaction energies to below chemical accuracy (1 kcal/mole), and the presence of significant outliers in even very large basis sets. I.e., it is insufficient to characterize a calculation by just identifying the exchange-correlation functional used because of the size of errors from all but the largest Gaussian basis that include semi-core polarization. Such model chemistries are relevant to many chemical applications, and can extract quantitative results through carefully engineered cancellation of error for instance in the prediction of trends (e.g., differences in reaction energies, $\Delta\Delta G$) or in application to homodesmotic reactions [32, 33].

- A positive observation is the apparent transferability (for this set of test molecules, reactions, and functionals) of basis sets between DFT functionals when computing reaction energies. Uncontracting or recontracting a basis for a given DFT functional can reduce error, but the residual error in the primitive set is typically seen to be larger than the contraction error.
- The multiwavelet basis provides a practical approach to reliable and direct computation of numerically-converged chemistry that for large molecules is both faster and more accurate than conventional Gaussian methods. However, Gaussian basis sets retain significant advantages at lower accuracy, or for smaller systems, or for dynamics, or for post-HF methods. This is due to more systematic cancellation of errors in computing chemical energy differences in atom-centered basis sets, and to it being hard in the multiwavelet basis to define a set of virtual orbitals as a basis for many-body models.

To facilitate reproducibility and use of this highly-curated data set in future studies, the SI includes all input geometries, input and output files, associated Python scripts that manipulated data or produced the plots, and files with extracted data in CSV format that is suitable for automated processing or importing into spreadsheets.

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TESSE

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